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**Updated Report on MPI, Load Balancing and
Resilience in Plasma Codes**

WP3: Algorithms and Libraries for Extreme-Scale Plasma Simulations

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Executive Summary

In this deliverable, we describe the current state of MPI usage, load balancing and implementation of resilience of the four plasma physics simulation codes BIT, PIconGPU, GENE/GENE-X and Vlasiator and the improvements done since D3.1 from last year. Furthermore, a summary of the overall algorithmic improvements in the codes is given. However, the work is not, yet, complete and hence still describes work in progress, which we will be updated throughout the remainder of the project.

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1 Introduction

This deliverable considers the state and progress of the plasma codes regarding efficient and reliable communication. Network communication is a significant bottleneck in these plasma codes for large node numbers - even more so in exascale computations. Load imbalances prevent utilization of the total available computing power and are thus considered in this document, too. Furthermore, with such large node counts as seen in supercomputers today and in the future on which our plasma codes run, the probability of failing nodes must be taken into account. This is why work is done to increase resilience by handling node failures.

This document is split into four main sections, each of which describing one of the tasks in this deliverable:

- an assessment of used MPI features and the performance state of the communication,
- a discussion of the work on load balancing,
- a short report on the resilience features of the codes and
- an overview of the work on overall algorithmic improvements.

In the last section, the work is summarized and a conclusion of the progress is given.

2 Updated Assessment of MPI Communication

This first section focuses on improving the communication behavior of all four targeted codes. In particular, it describes a workload analysis of BIT, a focus on compression and communication overlap in GENE/GENEX, scaling properties of PIconGPU, and improvements to ghost cell exchange and partitioning in Vlasiator.

2.1 BIT

As described in [12] and reported in D3.1, an initial assessment of BIT1 code performance included a study of MPI communication patterns. This was further investigated in [9] through the integration of openPMD BP4 instrumentation to analyze its impact on MPI communication and load balancing. `CrayPat` and `Cray Apprentice2` were employed to investigate the performance of the BIT1 openPMD BP4 application across various scales, ranging from small-scale runs on a single node to large-scale runs on up to 100 nodes. `CrayPat` facilitated code instrumentation, while `Cray Apprentice2` supported interactive, graphical performance analysis and visualization, particularly for strong scaling experiments.

Fig. 1 illustrates the performance breakdown of BIT1, focusing on the impact of the openPMD BP4 backend. For small-scale runs, these tools provided a detailed analysis of function calls with significant exclusive sample hits, averaged across ranks. Notable contributors to the performance profile included functions such as “arrj” (19.8%), “adios2::AggregateCollectiveMetadata” (11.9%), “MPI_Wait” (25.5%), “avq_0” (10.2%)

Figure 1: Percentage breakdown of the BIT1 openPMD BP4 Ionization call functions, where most of the execution time is attributed to these functions across small to large scale runs. As anticipated, the `arrj` sorting function (highlighted in blue) dominates the runtime, increasing from 19.8% to 40%. However, there is a notable decrease in the “MPI_Wait” function, dropping from 25.5% to 12.9%. The analysis utilized the CrayPat & Cray Apprentice2 tools.

and “adios2::helper::CommReqImplMPI::Wait” (5.5%), which collectively revealed critical aspects of BIT1’s computational and communication interplay. Additionally, “move0” (9.7%) and “nmove” (5.2%) were identified as significant contributors to execution time, with the remaining functions accounting for 2.8% of the sample hits.

Scaling to 100 nodes revealed a different performance profile. Despite fewer total sample hits, functions like “arrj” (40%), “avq_0” (21.3%), “MPI_Wait” (12.9%), “move0” (9.3%), and “nmove” (4.5%) remained key contributors to execution time. However, the impact of “adios2::AggregateCollectiveMetadata” dropped to 3.4%. Interestingly, “MPI_Wait” decreased from 25.5% on a single node to 12.9% on 100 nodes, contrary to the usual increase in MPI communication with more nodes. This reduction is attributed to the optimization of MPI communication by openPMD with the ADIOS2 BP4 backend, as highlighted in [12].

Based on the CrayPat & Cray Apprentice2 results, further investigation of MPI communication and load balancing in BIT1 openPMD BP4 simulations using IPM was conducted to assess potential trade-offs in the “MPI_Wait” function. IPM provided insights into parallel and MPI performance by capturing the computation and communication activities of BIT1. Fig.2 shows the MPI aggregated communication time for the 100-node BIT1 openPMD BP4 simulation across 12,800 cores, with “MPI_Gatherv” (67.65%) dominating the communication time, highlighting the need to optimize data gathering. Significant time is also spent in “MPI_Recv” (19.04%) and “MPI_Wait” (5.76%), pointing to possible inefficiencies in message handling and synchronization. Additionally, the memory usage per node is balanced, with the highest at 33 GB and the lowest at 29 GB.

More details and/or insights into BIT1 optimization strategies, particularly in data gathering and message handling are published by Jeremy J. Williams et al. [12, 9, 10, 11].

Figure 2: MPI aggregated communication time for the BIT1 openPMD BP4 simulation on Dardel using 100 nodes, totaling 12,800 MPI processes.

2.2 GENE/GENEX

In combination with WP4, we started using compression in combination with the MPI point-to-point communication. As compressing the data takes time, we split the data into blocks which are then compressed, sent/received and decompressed blockwise with a maximal overlap of computation and communication employed, effectively hiding part of the compression overhead. The partitioned communication primitives introduced in the MPI-4.0 standard partially reflect this approach, by simplifying the process of splitting the data and handling the different partitions that need to be communicated. We have successfully tested this approach on a simplified proxy code simulating an existing neighbor exchange in GENE. Unfortunately, we have to use the GPU for compression and ideally use a streamed approach to achieve the necessary overlap of computation and communication. This is not yet supported by current MPI standards, which is the reason why we decided to use the Nvidia Collective Communication Library (NCCL) for implementing the approach in the end application. Together with another national project (DaREXA-F), we are working on supporting a proposal to the MPI Forum that enables the usage of accelerator streams within the MPI library. A publication is in preparation to show the results in more detail.

Another brand-new feature of MPI are the MPI Sessions, which have been investigated also in combination with WP4 in the framework for in-situ analysis. While performance results are still early due to early implementations, the functionality of MPI Sessions was crucial to add the needed ability to dynamically change the resources. This enables a functional split between the core application and the in-situ component, further, can lead to a much better resource usage.

The network communication with compression has been modeled in a simple toy program to understand when the compression is viable and set requirements on the performance of the used compression algorithm as well as the computing performance of

Figure 3: GENE theoretical limits on effective throughput with data compression on raven. Raven GPU nodes have doubled network bandwidth.

Figure 4: GENE measurement results of simulated "dummy" compression on raven for different numbers of communication pairs and filling strategies.

Figure 5: GENE maximum combined compression and decompression time per message to achieve a given speedup.

the hardware where the compression is done. The compression is simulated by cutting off part of the data before sending a packet and filling the trailing non-transmitted space with one of three filling strategies:

- no memory operation: the space is left undefined,
- zero: the space is filled with zero bytes or
- copy: the space is filled with repeated copies of the transmitted data.

In the toy program, pairs of processes on two different nodes communicate by simultaneously sending and receiving fixed-size (4 MiB) floating-point data packets. The modeled theoretical limits are shown in figure 3, figure 4 shows measurements of the effective throughput on the supercomputer raven at the MPCDF and 5 shows the combined time that can be used for compression and decompression while achieving a given speedup.

Work on benchmarking a lossy floating-point compression on FPGA-based SmartNICs and a comparison to GPU compression throughput is ongoing.

Further, high-performance MPI performance counters will that are currently work-in-progress will be used to assess and potentially optimize the node scheduling algorithm of GENE.

2.3 PIConGPU

Figure 6: Strong scaling of PIConGPU using standard MPI (blue dots) and GPU-aware MPI (green triangles) As can be seen we see a slight but not significant speed up due to GPU-aware MPI. This is due to the fact that communication in PIConGPU is already running concurrently with computation.

PIConGPU fully supports GPU-aware MPI for both Nvidia and AMD GPUs. It further uses both NCCL and RCCL as well as libfabric for in-situ workflows, as detailed in D4.2. In 2024 we have measured strong and weak scaling on LUMI with and without GPU-aware MPI, see Fig. 6. It shows that execution of inter-node communication concurrently with computation is already implemented well.

2.4 Vlasiator

During 2024, the Vlasiator team finalized work on an alternative approach to solving advection equations, specifically in an application to solving the six-dimensional Vlasov equation for modelling space plasmas. This alternative approach builds on communicating larger ghost domains around the partition assigned to each MPI task and computing on these ghost cells allows for coalescing several discrete communication calls into one. This approach needs more overall data communication and computation, but provides interesting new avenues for the balancing of computational load between MPI tasks. A manuscript detailing this algorithmic development along with benchmarking results and discussion of these trade-offs was accepted for publication in the workshop proceedings of the EUROPAR 2024 conference, held in Madrid in August 2024 [8]. Discussion in the manuscript also touches upon how it may assist in developing other algorithmic improvements, and how the transition to heterogeneous CPU-GPU architectures may impact its usefulness.

3 Updated Assessment of Load Balancing

Load balance and the ability to execute load balancing are closely connected to communication analysis, as their effect often is connected to long wait and idle times in communication. Good load balance is, therefore, critical. For this reason, all four codes have some kind of balancing mechanism, which current state is detailed below.

3.1 BIT

BIT1 has been upgraded with particle load balancing across MPI ranks. It is integrated in the checkpointing mechanism and can be triggered during a *restore-from-checkpoint* by adding the `--load_balance` parameter to the BIT1 executable, e.g.: `/path-to-exe/BIT1 input_file restore_file --load_balance`.

Without particle load balancing, each MPI rank solves an equal share of the domain (uniform domain decomposition), i.e. the `[rmpi*nc:(rmpi+1)*nc]` cells interval, where *rmpi* is the MPI rank and *nc* is the total number of cells divided by the total number of MPI ranks. In this setup, the MPI ranks may have very different number of particles in their respective domains, as shown in Fig. 7a, bottom plot.

With particle load balancing, the total number of particles in the whole domain is divided by the total number of MPI ranks, as shown in Fig. 7b – bottom plot, which may lead to very different cell intervals across MPI ranks (non-uniform domain decomposition $\sim 1/N_{particles}$). This feat is achieved with little to no additional expense on restore time by using the parallel read capability of openPMD with the ADIOS2 backend (specifically, we use the binary pack version 4 – BP4). For the simple example presented in Fig. 7, load balance led to a speedup of the main loop of around 1.26x. For production cases, where the number of simulation particles is important, the speedup from load balance is expected to be much higher.

Figure 7: BIT1 restore from checkpoint without (a) and with (b) particle load balancing.

3.2 GENE/GENEX

GENE and GENEX do not suffer of dynamic load imbalance. The only origin of a static load imbalance for the GENE code comes from the different size of the gyroradii of the electrons and ions and for different μ grid points. But this kind of load balance manifests in different fill grades of the gyro matrices, hence are only seen in the gyroaveraging procedure. As this part of the code only takes a small portion of the runtime, the load imbalance does not hurt at the moment. It could also be mitigated by using a different parallelization [3].

3.3 PIConGPU

PIConGPU supports node-local dynamic load balancing of its central data types, super cells and particle frames. It further supports static load balancing via domain decomposition on the inter-node level. Inter-node load balancing is currently the main bottleneck to increase strong scaling performance, but does not usually affect weak scaling significantly.

We are currently investigating improvements to the alpaka library (see D5.2) to support better dynamic load balancing. It is clear that missing inter-node load balancing currently increases GPU memory usage across nodes significantly, thus limiting the available GPU memory to store large systems rather than limiting performance. In-situ coupling (D4.2) and advanced memory allocators (D5.2) are building blocks towards better memory usage on exascale compute systems.

3.4 Vlasiator

Vlasiator utilizes the Zoltan [1] load balancing for dynamic decomposition of the spatial domain over all available MPI tasks. Each spatial cell in the domain can have a dynamically varying phase-space complexity, with block counts (directly correlating with memory and processing time usage) varying by up to two orders of magnitude.

An investigation into the load balancing algorithms provided by Zoltan was conducted. In particular, the following algorithms were tested: recursive coordinate and inertial

bisection, graph and hypergraph partitioning using Zoltan’s native partitioner PHG, and Hilbert Space-Filling Curve (HSFC) partitioning. Of these, the HSFC method turned out the fastest at a speedup of 3.0% in small-scale tests. A box plot of the compared algorithms is provided in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Vlasiator comparison of velocity-space cells propagated per core-second, statistics over twelve runs lasting five simulation seconds each. Shown are performance values for five different load balancing metrics supported by the Zoltan library.

Figure 9: Vlasiator comparison of velocity-space cells propagated per core per second, statistics over twelve runs lasting five simulation seconds. Shown are performance values for eight different implementations of Hilbert space-filling curve partitioning. Z is the three-dimensional Z-curve, Octree is Zoltan’s original Hilbert curve definition, and the rest are sourced from Haverkort [4].

Further work was done on improving the curve choice of HSFC. While the Hilbert curve is uniquely defined in two dimensions, it can be extended to three dimensions in an arbitrary amount of ways. The curve choice in Zoltan is identified by Haverkort [4] as Butz [2]; however, many others have superior *locality*, which measures the ratio of distance between points in three-dimensional space and on the curve. Zoltan’s Hilbert curve was tested against the Z-curve, a re-implementation of the Butz curve and five

other curves from Haverkort [4]. Testing showed a further speedup of 1.2% over Zoltan's implementation for Beta, the best alternative curve tested. A box plot of the curves is provided in Figure 9.

4 Updated Assessment of Resilience

This chapter reports on advances in all four codes wrt. resilience, specifically in the currently widely adopted checkpointing techniques. In addition, for some codes new monitoring options have been added to detect failures, as this helps in validating the chosen approaches.

4.1 BIT

BIT1 checkpointing to disk and restore from disk can be done using either the original serial I/O or the parallel I/O implemented as part of Plasma-PEPSC, or a combination of both, depending on the value of *origdmp* in the input file during checkpoint and restore.

If *origdmp*=1, then checkpoint/restore uses serial write/read. If *origdmp*=2, then checkpoint/restore uses parallel I/O. By default, only the last checkpoint is saved as it is the only checkpoint needed to restore the simulation. To keep all checkpoints, e.g. for diagnostics, `--append` must be added at the end of the usage command.

When streaming is activated, checkpointing to disk is not done automatically. To checkpoint to disk from streaming `openpmd-pipe` must be used in order to catch the stream from memory and save it to disk.

It is not possible to restore from serial I/O files (.dmp) with load balancing, directly. A workaround is to restore from .dmp files without `--load_balance`, checkpoint to .bp4 file format (*origdmp*=2) and finally restore from bp4 using load balancing.

In the same way, it is not possible to checkpoint to serial .dmp files using load balancing, directly. A workaround is to checkpoint with load balancing to .bp4 file format (*origdmp*=2), restore from bp4 without load balancing and finally checkpoint to serial .dmp files.

4.2 GENE/GENEX

GENE and GENEX, both codes use a regular checkpointing mechanism which writes out the distribution function to disk from time to time either in standard Fortran binary format or in a portable HDF5 format. In the case of failure, a restart from this file is possible. Usually the writing of the file is not very time consuming at the current scales and systems. A careful estimation on how it will behave on Exascale systems is planned.

4.3 PIConGPU

PIConGPU uses checkpointing as provided by the openPMD library, providing high throughput parallel file I/O. Our strategy is to write regular checkpoints, check their validity and then delete older ones once disk usage becomes an issue. For full system runs, our experience on many top ten HPC systems has been that the project disk space

is not sufficient for complete system checkpoints as they approach the size of several hundred Terabytes even with compression.

4.4 Vlasiator

The Vlasiator team has implemented a HPC monitor script (on all currently used HPC clusters) to warn users in case available disk quota is such that checkpointing or file I/O is at risk of failing. The script is integrated to our team chat platform’s API, enabling straight-to-the-user notification, as other systems such as email notifications are not necessarily supported by EuroHPC platforms. Code development is underway to perform success checking on all disk output and warn the user in all output logs if a write is unsuccessful.

Further resilience improvement implementations within the PLASMA-PEPSC project for Vlasiator are pending results of data compression studies in another EuroHPC project (Inno4scale-2023 project 101118139 ASTERIX). Planned future improvements include in-situ validation of written data, checking that file headers and footers are correctly readable, as well as staggered higher-cadence rolling buffer checkpointing in order to reduce disk space requirements.

5 Overall Algorithmic Improvements

This final section adds an additional class of observations and improvements, which — while not a direct part of the tasks in WP3 and is collected over the remaining work on the codes — directly contributes to the discussion on code performance and optimization: algorithmic improvements, which then directly impact aspects like communication, scaling and load balance.

5.1 BIT

The recent profiling of BIT1 revealed a possibility to optimize a number of kernels by manually vectorizing them. Accordingly, the vectorization of two frequently called kernels has been performed leading to measurable speedup of simulations: vectorized kernel performance increased by the factor 5 in average.

5.2 GENE/GENEX

Both GENE and GENEX utilize fixed velocity space grids ($v_{||}$ and μ) to predict the density and temperature profiles for the target ITER case. Due to the significant temperature differences across the profiles, a large number of grid points are required to adequately resolve all regions, making simulations computationally expensive. The Block-Structured Grids (BSG) method offers a solution by efficiently reducing the number of grid points while maintaining accuracy. Significant efforts in algorithmic advancements have been focused on developing the BSG approach in GENEX as GENE already has a working implementation. The idea of BSG is to subdivide the radial direction in a small number of blocks (3-5 blocks are usually enough) and change the extent of the velocity space grids in dependence of the background temperature, but keep the same number of grid

points. With this approach, which has been first implemented for GENE in ref.[5, 6], we can reach a high resolution with a fixed number of grid points for the price of a more complicated implementation.

Figure 10 gives a rough picture of the generation of blocks in the poloidal plane for GENEX. The region close to the core (colored red) will have a higher temperature, therefore, the length of the velocity space will be much wider compared to the region colored in green which is at a relatively lower temperature. If the number of points in the velocity space is kept constant, the resolution requirements are met in both the regions at a much lower cost.

Figure 10: Generation of two blocks based on the radial distance in the poloidal plane.

At the time of writing, the development of BSG in GENEX is progressing well. Currently, the implementation is focused on the CPU, with plans to extend it to GPUs following further validation and verification of the technique. The development primarily revolves around two core classes: the grid generation class and the operator class. The grid generation class leverages information from the RZ grid (in the poloidal plane) to construct the velocity space grid for each block. As previously noted, the number of grid points remains constant within each block, while the domain width is allowed to vary. Consequently, the grid points are not aligned across block boundaries, necessitating interpolations for stencils that span these boundaries. To address this, the BSG operator class provides the necessary routines for performing these interpolations in velocity space. Most of the fundamental components of this method have already been implemented and integrated into the code repository. Furthermore, a comprehensive set of operators required to evaluate this approach has been implemented using BSG and successfully merged into the repository.

In the next stage, we will perform rigorous verification studies to ensure that numerical accuracy remains consistent and that the results are both robust and reliable. This will be followed with testing the implementation for real physical cases to make sure the results obtained are comparable to the current non-BSG runs. Following this, the work is planned for 2025 to include a GPU implementation.

5.3 PIConGPU

To better support vectorization and large vector length registers, work was done on the alpaka library (see D5.2) to investigate how SIMD parallelism can be integrated with the dominant GPU inspired highly multi-threaded, parallelism model.

PIConGPU relies on MallocMC for on-device memory allocation, since vendor default allocation policies are seen to be a bottleneck. Recent work on MallocMC has been done to simplify the design, and improve performance. The redesign enables further optimization as it is now possible to have custom allocation policies depending on the practical data access patterns and use case.

Recent work on PIConGPU has also been on adding new high accuracy algorithm implementations for the TWEAC laser which is now under further testing.

Further work on PIConGPU and its ecosystem, alpaka, MallocMC etc, has been done to move the codebase from C++17 to C++20, which enables use of new language features. This work is going to be continued into 2025, and is expected to bring usability and performance improvements.

5.4 Vlasiator

Improvements to Vlasiator’s adaptive mesh refinement system have been published in [7], with further improvements to the physics-based algorithms under development allowing for refinement based on not additional parametrizations such as a kinetic plasma beam instability threshold.

Furthermore, a memory management issue was causing Vlasiator production runs to encounter out-of-memory issues when performing aggressive load re-balancing or refinement adjustments to the grid. This was investigated heavily in 2024, and improvements to chunking of large data transfers were implemented. Ultimately, a corrective measure was implemented through adding extra API hooks to the `jemalloc` memory management library used by Vlasiator. When chunking a large MPI transfer into several smaller transfers, thus reducing the amount of transfer buffers required at a single time, a manual purging of memory pages active in `jemalloc` was required, as the standard time-based purging mechanism would not trigger between chunks.

6 Conclusion

Ongoing efforts in multiple aspects of the BIT, GENE/GENEX, PIConGPU and Vlasiator workloads have been described in this document. Highlights include the analysis of communication patterns in the BIT workload, compression and communication and computation overlap in GENE/GENEX, pushing scaling boundaries in PIConGPU, and improvements to ghost cell exchange and partitioning in Vlasiator. The performance and scaling aspects of MPI efficiency and load balancing have been documented. These efforts have been presented and published in relevant research communities, and their references have been provided in this document.

Research on the topic of resilience has been reported, specifically in the currently widely adopted checkpointing techniques. In addition, monitoring has been added to

detect failures. The use of monitoring can help our workloads confirm whether checkpointing techniques are sufficient for them, or whether we should be exploring emerging techniques, such as MPI runtime systems like Open MPI's User Level Failure Mitigation (ULFM). Resiliency is an important aspect to track, considering how the increased number of computation units relates to the probability of failures. Our simulations can last from several hours to even weeks, and a failure can mean the loss of significant energy and time.

The algorithms that drive our workloads have naturally been the focus of further research. Algorithms determine how workloads scale, as they are mapped to hardware resources. Their improvements, although rare in established domains, can be much more significant than improvements in other areas, such as MPI efficiency.

Overall, we expect the aggregated effect of all these independent efforts will bring significant increases of efficiency and scalability potential for the Plasma-PEPSC workloads. Further ongoing codesign efforts with libraries will also contribute to these improvements in the near future.

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